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Implementing Fuzzy Multi Attribute Decision Making (F-MADM) Weighted Product to Determine the Office Location

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Abstract

For a company, determining the location of a business is very important because it supports the company's business success. PT GVK Services Indonesia will establish a branch office in Indonesia and choose Jakarta as the central location of its business. However, the company is currently experiencing difficulties in determining the most strategic location. There are many aspects that must be considered in terms of choosing the office location such as rental rates, facilities, distances, and stakeholders. To solve this problem, the Fuzzy Multi Attribute Decision Making (F-MADM) Weighted Product method was chosen to assist the management in determining the location of PT GVK Services Indonesia. The analysis results regarding the use of these methods provide the most strategic location information.

Keywords: *Weighted Product, Location, PT. GVK Services Indonesia*

1. Introduction

GVK Power and Infrastructure Limited is an Indian company engaged in various important sectors of the economy, including in the fields of energy, resources, transportation, and airports. At present, GVK manages, operates and develops GVK Chhatrapati Shivaji International Airport (GVK CSIA) in Mumbai, India. Due to consideration of business locations in Indonesia, GVK chose Jakarta as the location of the branch office. Utilization of the Decision Support System is expected to assist the GVK in the process of selecting branch office location in Jakarta. There have been several studies that discuss the determination of business locations or branch offices. The study, conducted by Ari Basuki (2011), uses the Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process method with Extent Analysis (FAHP Extent Analysis) in the selection of distribution warehouse locations using five criteria, namely transportation conditions, proximity to consumers, investment costs, market conditions, and location. Based on the above explanation, the author decides to conduct research aimed at finding the best location for the GVK Services Indonesia office by utilizing the Fuzzy Multi Attribute Decision Making Weighted Product method.

2. Theoretical Basis

The choice of the business location of an organization or company will affect the overall risk and profit of the company because location greatly influences fixed and variable costs in the medium and long term. Decision making is the process of choosing actions (among various alternatives) to achieve one or several goals (Chen, Xiaohong., Takahara, & Yasuhiko: 2000). In general, DSS is an interactive computer-based system. It helps make decisions by utilizing data and models to solve structured problems. Meanwhile, DSS, in particular, is a system that supports the work of a manager or group of managers in solving semi-structured problems by providing information or proposals leading to certain decisions. Fuzzy logic is an appropriate way to map an input space into an output space. The modern concept of uncertainty was created by Zadeh (1965), who introduced a theory that has objects from fuzzy sets that have inaccurate boundaries and membership in fuzzy sets. In addition, it is not in the form of true or false logic but is expressed in degrees. Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) is a decision-making method to determine the best alternative from a number of alternatives based on certain criteria. Fuzzy Multiple Attribute Decision Making (FMADM) is a method used to find

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optimal alternatives from a number of alternatives with certain criteria. The essence of Fuzzy MADM is to determine the weight value for each attribute. Then, it is continued with the ranking process which will select the alternatives that have been given. WPM is one of the models in a decision support system that uses multiplication to link attribute ratings. In this case, the rating of each attribute must first be raised with the weight of the attribute in question (Yoon, 1989 in Kusumadewi).

3. Research Method

The study was conducted on overall building data that has the potential to be an alternative choice. Primary data obtained by conducting surveys directly to the location while secondary data obtained from property agents. Data collection was conducted in November 2016.

Figure 1.
Research Framework

PT GVK Services Indonesia intends to establish a new business branch. To realize the plan, PT GVK Services Indonesia must choose the right location to develop the business. Based on this matter, the purpose of this decision is to find the best location to establish a new business branch for PT GVK Services, Indonesia. The alternative of location for new business branches is strategic locations and business value. For this reason, the management chose a location in the middle of the city that included Kuningan, Thamrin, Sudirman, and Kemayoran areas.

The management of PT GVK Services Indonesia has several considerations in determining the location of new business branches in Jakarta. Following is a description of each criterion under consideration by PT GVK Services Indonesia.

1. Cost. In the case of leasing office space, the costs that must be included in the company's planning budget are the costs of renting the room, i.e. the costs that the company must pay to the building owner or room owner.
2. Facilities. Given the variety of workers and work tasks that are carried out, it is not always easy to choose suitable office space where facilities also need to be considered.
3. Accessibility or level of convenience achieved by users, to an object, service, and environment.
4. Potential Disasters. The importance of knowing potential disasters in determining office locations is so that we care about and understand what supporting facilities we will get

The selection of branch office location of PT GVK Services Indonesia applies the Fuzzy Multi Attribute Decision Making (FMADM) Weighted Product (WP) method. Fuzzy calculation in the WP method is carried out on the weighting of criteria values based on weight graphs and produces crisp values, which will then be calculated with the weights on each alternative.

Discussion

GVK is one of the world's largest private airport owners and operators. It manages Mumbai and Bangalore International airports in India and has annual traffic of more than 70 million passengers per year. In addition, it handles 45 flights and 33 flights each at two airports. The results of the fuzzy analysis begin with determining

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the weights of the fuzzy values of the criteria and alternatives. Fuzzy value determination of criteria and alternatives is performed by using fuzzy set graphs and the determination of ratings or weights is based on PT GVK Services Indonesia’s policy. Rating for each decision criteria is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Interest Rating for each Criterion

Criteria	Weigh	Crisp Value
C1.1	High	0.9
C1.2	High	0.9
C1.3	High	0.9
C1.4	Medium	0.5
C1.5	Medium	0.5
C1.6	Medium	0.5
C1.7	Low	0.1
C2.1	High	0.9
C2.2	Medium	0.5
C2.3	Low	0.1
C2.4	Medium	0.5
C2.5	High	0.9
C2.6	Medium	0.5
C3.1	High	0.9
C3.2	High	0.9
C3.3	High	0.9
C3.4	Medium	0.5
C3.5	Medium	0.5
C4	High	0.9

After the interest rating for each criterion is obtained, the next is to determine the suitability rating of all alternatives against the criteria. Match rating is the inclusion of alternative values for each criterion. Matching ratings of decision criteria and alternatives can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Match Rating of Each Alternative and Each Criteria

Alternatives	Criteria																			
	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C2.6	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3	C3.4	C3.5	C4.1	
A1	1,00	0	0,75	0,1	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,5	0,25	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,5	0,5	
A2	1,00	0	0,75	0,1	0,1	0,9	0,5	0,5	1	0,1	0,5	0,1	0,9	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,5	
A3	0,25	1	0,75	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,9	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,9	0,5	
A4	0,50	0,25	0,75	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,5	1	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,9	0,5	
A5	0,25	1	0,75	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,25	0,1	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,5	
A6	0,25	0,75	0,75	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	
A7	0,75	0	0,75	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,5	1	0,1	0,9	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	
A8	0,50	1	0,75	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,5	1	0,1	0,9	0,9	0,1	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,1	
A9	0,75	1	0,75	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	1	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	
A10	0,25	0,75	0,75	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,75	0,1	0,9	0,9	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	
A11	0,25	0,75	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,1	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,1	
A12	0,25	0,25	0,5	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,9	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,9	
A13	0,50	0	0,25	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,5	1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,5	0,9	0,9	

Furthermore, the weighting normalization or improvement of weights to the criteria is carried out; thus

$$\sum W_j = 1 \text{ by using Formula 2.1.}$$

$$W_{11} = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.9}{12.3} = 0.07$$

$$W_{12} = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.9}{12.3} = 0.07$$

$$W_{13} = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.9}{12.3} = 0.07$$

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$$W_{14} = \frac{0.5}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.5}{12.3} = 0.04$$

$$W_{15} = \frac{0.5}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.5}{12.3} = 0.04$$

$$W_{16} = \frac{0.5}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.5}{12.3} = 0.04$$

$$W_{17} = \frac{0.1}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.1}{12.3} = 0.01$$

$$W_{21} = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.9}{12.3} = 0.07$$

$$W_{22} = \frac{0.5}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.5}{12.3} = 0.04$$

$$W_{23} = \frac{0.1}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.1}{12.3} = 0.01$$

$$W_{24} = \frac{0.5}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.5}{12.3} = 0.04$$

$$W_{25} = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.9}{12.3} = 0.07$$

$$W_{26} = \frac{0.5}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.5}{12.3} = 0.04$$

$$W_{31} = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.9}{12.3} = 0.07$$

$$W_{32} = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.9}{12.3} = 0.07$$

$$W_{33} = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.9}{12.3} = 0.07$$

$$W_{34} = \frac{0.5}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.5}{12.3} = 0.04$$

$$W_{35} = \frac{0.5}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.5}{12.3} = 0.04$$

$$W_{41} = \frac{0.9}{0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.5+0.1+0.9+0.5+0.1+0.5+0.9+0.5+0.9+0.9+0.9+0.5+0.5+0.9} = \frac{0.9}{12.3} = 0.07$$

Normalization of all criteria weights can be found in Table 3

Table 3. Normalization of Criteria Weight

Criteria Weight	Normalization
W ₁₁	0,07
W ₁₂	0,07
W ₁₃	0,07
W ₁₄	0,04
W ₁₅	0,04
W ₁₆	0,04
W ₁₇	0,01
W ₂₁	0,07
W ₂₂	0,04
W ₂₃	0,01
W ₂₄	0,04
W ₂₅	0,07
W ₂₆	0,04
W ₃₁	0,07
W ₃₂	0,07
W ₃₃	0,07
W ₃₄	0,04
W ₃₅	0,04
W ₄₁	0,07
ΣW	1

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In a calculation, the type of W_j criteria should be determined. Calculation of Vector S is carried out by lifting the weight of the criteria (W_j) to the match value of alternatives and criteria (X_{ij}). Criteria weights are positive for the profit attribute and negative for the cost attribute. The following is the S_i calculation for each alternative, using Formula 2.2

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_1 &= (1^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.01})(0.5^{-0.07})(0.3^{0.04}) \\
 &\quad (0.1^{0.01})(0.5^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.9^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.05^{-0.07})(0.9^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.04}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 1.1735 \\
 S_2 &= (1^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.01})(0.5^{-0.07})(1^{0.04}) \\
 &\quad (0.1^{0.01})(0.5^{0.04})(0.1^{0.07})(0.9^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.05^{-0.07})(0.9^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.04}) \\
 &\quad (0.9^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 1.2010 \\
 S_3 &= (0.25^{-0.07})(1^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.01}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.07})(0.5^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.5^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.9^{0.04})(0.9^{0.07})(0.05^{-0.07}) \\
 &\quad (0.9^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 1.2382 \\
 S_4 &= (0.5^{-0.07})(0.25^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.01}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.07})(1^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.5^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.5^{0.04})(0.9^{0.07})(0.05^{-0.07})(0.9^{-0.07}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 1.5613 \\
 S_5 &= (0.25^{-0.07})(1^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.01}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.07})(0.3^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.5^{0.04})(0.9^{0.07})(0.5^{0.04})(0.9^{0.07})(0.5^{-0.07})(0.9^{-0.07}) \\
 &\quad (0.9^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 1.5796 \\
 S_6 &= (0.25^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.01}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.07})(0.5^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.5^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.9^{0.04})(0.1^{0.07})(0.1^{-0.07}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 1.9709 \\
 S_7 &= (0.75^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.01})(0.5^{-0.07})(1^{0.04}) \\
 &\quad (0.1^{0.01})(0.9^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.9^{0.04})(0.1^{0.07})(0.1^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 2.1153 \\
 S_8 &= (0.5^{-0.07})(1^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.01}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.07})(1^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.9^{0.04})(0.9^{0.07})(0.1^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.1^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 1.9486 \\
 S_9 &= (0.75^{-0.07})(1^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.01}) \\
 &\quad (0.1^{-0.07})(1^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.1^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.5^{0.04})(0.1^{0.07})(0.5^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 2.0055 \\
 S_{10} &= (0.25^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.01}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.07})(0.8^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.9^{0.04})(0.9^{0.07})(0.5^{0.04})(0.1^{0.07})(0.5^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &\quad (0.1^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 2.1472 \\
 S_{11} &= (0.25^{-0.07})(0.75^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.01})(0.1^{-0.07}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.9^{0.04})(0.9^{0.07})(0.9^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.1^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.07}) \\
 &\quad (0.5^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.07})
 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 1.7647 \\
 S12 &= (0.25^{-0.07})(0.25^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.01})(0.9^{-0.07})(0.5^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.5^{0.04})(0.1^{0.07})(0.5^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.1^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 1.4951 \\
 S13 &= (0.5^{-0.07})(0.25^{-0.07})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.1^{-0.04})(0.5^{-0.01})(0.5^{-0.07})(1^{0.04})(0.1^{0.01})(0.1^{0.04})(0.1^{0.07})(0.5^{0.04})(0.5^{0.07})(0.1^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.07})(0.5^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.04})(0.9^{-0.07}) \\
 &= 1.6330
 \end{aligned}$$

The results of the overall calculation of *Si* vector can be found in Table 4.

Table 4. Calculation results of *Si* vector

Area	Vector S
Standard Chartered	1.1735
Satrio Tower	1.2010
RDTX	1.2382
Menara Palma	1.5613
88 Kota Casablanca	1.5796
Menara Topas	1.9709
MNC Tower	2.1153
Menara Thamrin	1.9486
Wisma BSG	2.0055
Equity Tower	2.1472
BEJ Tower II	1.7647
RMCI Tower	1.4951
KEM Tower	1.6330

After the S vector value in each alternative is obtained, the next step is to rank them. This ranking process uses Formula 2.3. *Vi* value is the *Si* value divided by the total sum of all S values.

The calculation of Vector V values is as follows:

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_1 &= \frac{11735}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{11735}{218339} = 0.054 \\
 V_2 &= \frac{12010}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{12010}{218339} = 0.055 \\
 V_3 &= \frac{12382}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{12382}{218339} = 0.057 \\
 V_4 &= \frac{15613}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{15613}{218339} = 0.072 \\
 V_5 &= \frac{15796}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{15796}{218339} = 0.072 \\
 V_6 &= \frac{19709}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{19709}{218339} = 0.090 \\
 V_7 &= \frac{21153}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{21153}{218339} = 0.097 \\
 V_8 &= \frac{19486}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{19486}{218339} = 0.089 \\
 V_9 &= \frac{20055}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{20055}{218339} = 0.092 \\
 V_{10} &= \frac{21472}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{21472}{218339} = 0.098 \\
 V_{11} &= \frac{17647}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{17647}{218339} = 0.081 \\
 V_{12} &= \frac{14951}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{14951}{218339} = 0.068 \\
 V_{13} &= \frac{16330}{11735+12010+12382+15613+15796+19709+21153+19486+20055+21472+17647+14951+16330} - \frac{16330}{218339} = 0.075
 \end{aligned}$$

The final step is the ranking process. The ranking results obtained by the 3 largest values, starting from the largest are $V_{10} = 0.098$, $V_7 = 0.097$, $V_9 = 0.092$. The whole calculation results can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Preference Ranking Results

Area	Vector V
Equity Tower	0.098
MNC Tower	0.097
Wisma BSG	0.092
Menara Topas	0.090
Menara Thamrin	0.089
BEJ Tower II	0.081
KEM Tower	0.075
SS Kota Casablanca	0.072
Menara Palma	0.072
RMCI Tower	0.068
RDTX	0.057
Satrio Tower	0.055
Standard Chartered	0.054

Out of the 13 alternative office locations, Equity Building has the highest preference value of 0.098. Thus, the choice for the location of PT GVK Services Indonesia’s office is Equity Building.

Table 6. Value of Each Criterion for Each Alternative

October 30, 2019

Alternatif	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C2.6	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3	C3.4	C3.5	C4
A1	400.000	30.000	4.500.000	0	84.850	2.160.000	720.000	19	South	Empty	Worth It	Worth It	08.00 AM - 06.00 PM	7,3	24,6	35,3	2,1	4	Medium
A2	450.000	30.000	5.000.000	0	0	3.000.000	550.000	22	West	Empty	Worth It	Not Available	08.00 AM - 06.00 PM	6,4	17,3	33,4	3,6	5,2	Medium
A3	200.000	92.500	3.500.000	56.565	84.850	2.160.000	540.000	27	North	Empty	Worth It	Worth It	08.00 AM - 06.00 PM	8,3	25,6	36,3	3,1	5	Medium
A4	250.000	50.000	3.500.000	0	0	833.333	-	15	West	Empty	Worth It	Worth It	07.30 AM - 06.00 PM	8,9	25,9	36,9	3,7	5,8	Medium
A5	175.000	92.500	3.500.000	0	0	1.000.000	550.000	29	South	Empty	Worth It	Very Worth It	07.30 AM - 06.00 PM	9,2	20,1	36,2	6,4	8	Medium
A6	210.000	80.000	3.500.000	150.000	0	1.300.000	450.000	15	North	Empty	Worth It	Worth It	08.00 AM - 06.00 PM	3,2	14,1	30,2	0,4	2	Medium
A7	275.000	47.000	3.500.000	0	0	750.000	-	22	West	Empty	Very Worth It	Worth It	07.30 AM - 06.00 PM	3,6	14,5	30,6	0,8	2,8	Medium
A8	250.000	95.000	4.500.000	0	0	500.000	-	13	West	Empty	Very Worth It	Very Worth It	07.30 AM - 02.00 PM	7,7	12,9	31,7	2,5	6,1	Low
A9	300.000	96.000	5.000.000	0	0	500.000	-	3	West	Empty	Not Available	Worth It	07.30 AM - 06.00 PM	4,9	15,8	31,9	2,1	3,7	Medium
A10	170.000	90.000	5.000.000	0	0	500.000	-	25	East	Empty	Very Worth It	Very Worth It	07.30 AM - 06.00 PM	4,4	15,4	31,4	1,6	3,2	Medium
A11	150.000	90.000	3.000.000	150.000	0	1.300.000	450.000	7	North	Empty	Very Worth It	Very Worth It	08.00 AM - 06.00 PM	7,7	12,9	31,7	2,5	6,1	Low
A12	165.000	50.000	3.000.000	0	0	1.000.000	800.000	33	North	Empty	Worth It	Not Available	07.30 AM - 06.00 PM	5,9	700 m	29,7	3,5	9	High
A13	245.000	45.000	1.000.000	0	0	1.000.000	800.000	17	West	Empty	Not Available	Not Available	07.30 AM - 06.00 PM	6,7	500 m	27,8	3,5	10,9	High

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of several alternative building locations using the Fuzzy Multi Attribute Decision Making (FMADM) Weighted Product method, it is concluded that the use of the Fuzzy Multi Attribute Decision Making (FMADM) Weighted Product (WP) method in the selection of office location has been successfully applied to PT GVK Services Indonesia which pointed to the Equity Building located in the SCBD region as the best location choice. The application of the Fuzzy Multi Attribute Decision Making (FMADM) method using the Weighted Product (WP) method has helped the management of PT GVK Services Indonesia to more effectively select office location.

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